

HISTORY OF THE CITY OF MARGILON AND HISTORICAL-CULTURAL MONUMENTS IN ITS SURROUNDINGS

Kambarova Dilorom Yusupovna

Fergana State University

professor of the department of foreign languages for humanities

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-2503-1669>

e-mail: kambarovad@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13989475>

Abstract: The emergence of the ancient city of Margilon is largely connected with the opening of the Great Silk Road. This city is famous as an industrial center for the production of silk fabrics. In the 10th century, Margilan was famous for its products not only in Central Asia, but also in the countries of the Far East and West.

Key words: Ancient Margilan, Great Silk, Hidayat work, Pur Siddiq, Turkestan

In the 12th century, Burkhaniddin Marginani, a famous expert and jurist, lived here. In his work "Hidaya" the norms of the agreement between landowners and farmers were developed and shown. Thanks to Burkhaniddin Marginani, we know that the characteristic feature of large land ownership in Central Asia, as in Iran, was that at that time the landowners did not run large farms on their fields and did not cultivate them using the labor of peasants dependent on their fields. The plots of land are divided into large and medium-sized parts and are leased to anyone who wants them. The people who got the land have become farmers. The landless and landless inhabitants of the nearby villages have become farmers. In Hidayat, the legal traditions and norms dating back to the work of Abu Yusuf Yaqub (end of the 8th century) "Kitab al-kharaj" are presented, on the other hand, the practice of quarter rent for several centuries up to the 12th century is highlighted. The special section about the feudal city talks about the condition of craftsmen. At the end of the 15th century and the beginning of the 16th century, Margilan became one of the most important cities in the Fergana Valley. Sultan Babur, one of Timur's great-grandsons, was born and grew up here, and he became the ruler of Fergana at the age of 11. Babur 22, who later founded the Great Babur Empire in India in 1525, was a great statesman, historian, poet and geographer. Fergana, Margilan and other cities are described in his works. In the 18th century, wonderful architectural structures and ensembles were built in Margilon, most of which have not reached our days. Among the preserved architectural monuments, the topic of pigeon-holing attracts attention. It consists of a mosque with a unique and wonderful design, a beautiful minaret, a rectangular courtyard with a mausoleum with a pediment and a dome, a gatehouse and a magnificent dovecote. The date of construction of the mausoleum, which forms the basis of the structure, is indicated as 1155 Hijri, i.e. 1742 AD. According to legends, Pur Siddiq, one of the saints, was buried here. There is a legend that one day Pur Siddiq, who was running away from strangers, hid in the cave here, and the pigeons built a nest at the mouth of the cave and closed it. People chasing after the saint saw pigeons sitting comfortably in their nest at the mouth of the cave and passed by him. Since then, Pur Siddiq, protected by doves, has been living in Kaparlik until now, and folk masters have conveyed the idea of peace and tranquility in the saint's mausoleum with the help of decorations. Among the architectural monuments of Margilon, the Shoud Mosque (beginning of the 19th century), which is an

example of national architecture, has been preserved. The 19th-century religious building is characterized by a grid of rectangular wooden blocks of various sizes, joined together without any glue or nails. In the center of the grill is a mirror image made of smooth pieces of wood without any patterns or decorations. However, in this case, the large rectangle is divided into four smaller rectangles, the outer rectangles are filled with intersecting equilateral and octagons - resulting in an elegant grid in the center. The star frame running above and below this structure is made by splitting large pieces of wood with grooves. Two medallions adorning the outer border give the pattern a special charm. The whole fence is surrounded by a border along the perimeter. Grills of this type and size are rare in other temples in the region. Many small mosques were built in the middle of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century. The earlier buildings are related to the past and are distinguished by the porches and ceilings of the interior rooms decorated with complex and bright patterns found in them. However, new pictures were added to these patterns, and watercolors replaced the velvety color of the previous glue patterns. The interior walls are made of alabaster, sometimes colored, and some parts are decorated with patterns. The mosques built later changed their appearance dramatically, iron roofs, sometimes large glass windows, slatted doors, iron fences and tin frames were used in their construction. Margilan, buried in gardens, was a great place for caravans to rest. Here it was possible to replenish food supplies and rest. Freedom-loving people, proud Sogds lived in Margilon from ancient times. The beginning of the 20th century was characterized by anti-colonial uprisings and strikes. One of the biggest uprisings against tsarism in the Turkestan region, against the recruitment of the local population to labor behind the front lines in the areas where the tsarist Russia was waging war, started in Margilon on July 4, 1916, and later spread to the entire Turkestan region. As in the past, Margilan remained a silk city. In 1928, the leading scientific center for silk production - the Research Institute of the Silk Industry of Uzbekistan was opened here. The general technical faculty of the Tashkent Textile Institute, the College of Textiles and Planning and Economics, and the Pedagogical College are operating in the city. Margilan is also famous for its cultural traditions. Poet Uvaisi lived here in the 19th century. In 1915, Hamza Hakimzada Niyazi taught children in one of Margilan schools. People's artist Tamarakhonim (Petrosyan) spent her childhood here. The next turn along the railway and highways is the city of Kokan. On this way, you have to pass the Big Fergana stream named after Usman Yusupov several times. In 1939, this canal was dug from the Norin River in 45 days, and its length is 270 km. The canal serves to irrigate almost the entire land of the Fergana Valley.

The star frame running above and below this structure is made by splitting large pieces of wood with grooves. Two medallions adorning the outer border give the pattern a special charm. The entire fence is surrounded by a border along the perimeter. Grills of this type and size are rare in other temples in the region. Many small mosques were built in the middle of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century. The earlier buildings are related to the past and are distinguished by the porches and ceilings of the interior rooms decorated with complex and bright patterns found in them. However, new pictures were added to these patterns, and watercolors replaced the velvety color of the previous glue patterns. The interior walls are made of alabaster, sometimes colored, and some parts are decorated with patterns. The mosques built later changed their appearance dramatically, iron roofs, sometimes large glass windows, slatted doors, iron fences and tin frames were used in their

construction. Margilan, buried in gardens, was a great place for caravans to rest. Here it was possible to replenish food supplies and rest. Freedom-loving people, proud Sogds lived in Margilon from ancient times. The beginning of the 20th century was characterized by anti-colonial uprisings and strikes. One of the biggest uprisings against tsarism in the Turkestan region, against the recruitment of the local population to labor behind the front lines in the areas where the tsarist Russia was waging war, started in Margilon on July 4, 1916, and later spread to the entire Turkestan region. As in the past, Margilan remained a silk city. In 1928, the leading scientific center for silk production - the Research Institute of the Silk Industry of Uzbekistan was opened here. The general technical faculty of the Tashkent Textile Institute, the College of Textiles and Planning and Economics, and the Pedagogical College are operating in the city. Margilan is also famous for its cultural traditions. Poet Uvaisi lived here in the 19th century. In 1915, Hamza Hakimzada Niyazi taught children in one of Margilan schools. People's artist Tamarakhonim (Petrosyan) spent her childhood here. The next turn along the railway and highways is the city of Kokan. On this way, you have to pass the Big Fergana stream named after Usman Yusupov several times. In 1939, this canal was dug from the Norin River in 45 days, and its length is 270 km. The canal serves to irrigate almost the entire land of the Fergana Valley.

Pirsiddiq complex is one of the oldest settlements of Margilan city. This place is also known as "Kaptarlimozor" and has become a sacred place of pilgrimage for the people of Margilan. On the occasion of the wedding, large-scale construction and beautification works are being carried out here. A beautiful complex is under construction. The remains of the most learned people in Margilan are buried in this place. Burkhaniddin Marginani's shrine was also located in this shrine. Maskur Chillakhona is being completely rebuilt. A mosque, a shrine, will be built in the complex, which occupies an area of 1.5 hectares. The construction works are being carried out by the craftsmen of Fergana Region "Repair of Historical Monuments" Limited Liability Company.

Ulgmozor shrine is located in Mashat quarter of the city. Popularly known as "Mashat Mozor" and "Chagga Mozor". Ethnographer A. Ch. Pisarchik said that this place is the oldest grave. According to information, Imam Abdulaziz ibn Abdurazzaq ibn Nasr ibn Ja'far ibn Sulayman ibn Sukkon al-Marginani was buried here. He was a very famous scientist. He educated many enlightened people. Extensive construction work is being carried out at the Maskur shrine. The masters of the construction team named Usta Shirin Murodov from Bukhara are leading here. With the painstaking work of florists, this shrine becomes even more beautiful. Masters from Samarkand and Karakalpakstan are working on the construction of the mausoleum and house-museum of Jahan Otin Uvaisi. More than 160 million soums worth of construction works are planned here.

A nation that preserves historical monuments like the apple of an eye and passes them on to future generations will surely be great. This is clearly demonstrated by the great creative works being carried out in the dear places of the ancient city of Margilan, which is about to celebrate its 2000th anniversary.

References:

1. Sayfullayeva Y. Activities of tourist itineraries and excursion service in museums and historical monuments. - 2022. - T. 2. - no. 11. - S. 369-375.

2. Akbarkhan son U. I. Organization of excursion service to historical and architectural monuments of Uzbekistan // Journal of interdisciplinary innovations and scientific research in Uzbekistan. - 2022. - T. 1. – no. 12. - S. 1041-1046.
3. Pakhlavon oglu M. F. The formation and development of the tourism industry in Uzbekistan (in 1991-2021, as an example of the Ferghana Valley) //online scientific journal of education and development analysis. - 2023. - T. 3. – no. 9. - S. 145-151.
4. Usmonovna O. U. History of cities along the Great Silk Road // Journal of new century innovations. - 2024. - T. 51. - no. 1. – S. 133-142.
5. Jiyemuratov A.S., daughter Rajabova M.A., son Amidullaev B.T. Tourism potential of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its development prospects //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. - 2023. - T. 2. – no. 8. - S. 66-69.

